

SOME ISSUES OF TEACHING INDEPENDENT THINKING THROUGH ACTIVATING THE WILL TO STUDY IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article deals with some issues of the formation of independent thinking skills in students through the desire to learn in the first stage of education in primary school, provides important methodological recommendations in this area.*

Keywords: *motive, desire to read, independent thinking skills, conscious outlook, teamwork, innovative thinking, creative thinking, "Learning to think independently" program.*

The development and expansion of the scope of education requires teachers of the present time to be instilled with practical knowledge. On this basis, the creation of a learning environment that is convenient for every student to achieve success is ensured through an innovative approach. At the first stage of education, the formation of independent thinking skills in primary school students through the desire to study requires a lot of effort and special skills from the teacher. Thinking skills help students to realize themselves, to correctly determine the future path of life, to correctly understand the essence of spiritual and moral values, to make the right decision in various problematic situations. helps to develop the mindset of doing. Experiments show that children observe quickly when working under the guidance of a teacher. This way leads to the formation of negative characteristics in a person, such as limitation of activities only within the framework of personal interests, lack of understanding of social problems and inability to solve them, and as a result, mental dependence.

It is a very effective way to encourage independent thinking by making more students want to read themselves so that they don't get used to it. Cultivating a conscious worldview in students is extremely important to transform them from free listeners to free participants. The student's independent activity in accomplishing this task has a multifaceted effect. It is known that working on the text is considered as the main type of work in the 1st-4th grade reading classes, forming a desire to read and teaching students to think independently.

Independent thinking in reading lessons is the ability to analyze the content of each text, to express one's attitude to the events and characters described in it, to create new situations related to the content of the text, and to find one's way out of a difficult situation. The ability to think independently also depends on the level of speech development. Teaching children to think independently from the elementary grades develops the ability to solve any problem without the help of others. In order to teach students to do independent work, even if little by little every day, first of all, it is necessary to mentally prepare them for independent activity, to feel confidence in their own opinion. One of the conditions for the mental development of students is to fully "remember" their tasks, understand the purpose of the work to be done, imagine, determine its plan and choose a work method, be able to independently find mistakes and correct them. it is important to pay special attention to what they know. It is useful to choose convenient methods for students to complete the task quickly and correctly, to approach the work creatively, to always ask leading

questions and recommend key words to organize it. It is natural that students with bright imaginations and insufficient vocabulary have difficulties in performing independent work in a quality manner. In order to attract the attention of students, mention the events in the text: "Why?", "Why is it like this?", "How do you think it should be?" it is necessary to stimulate his thoughts by asking questions like The "Stop reading" strategy gives effective results in the development of students' thinking and independent thinking. This method creates a foundation for the formation of research culture in the student and, in general, the formation of a thinking person. (See. Akramova GR. Development of students' critical thinking in the process of general secondary education through the "stop reading" strategy. "Modern education" magazine, 2017, 5. pp. 70-74). If the student is satisfied with the first independent work, his interests increase and he starts to do new types of work. This, in turn, increases the child's independent thinking. The types of independent work should be carefully planned by the teacher, based on a certain goal and systematic.

Recommendations for the development of independent creative thinking:

- offer solutions to problematic issues to do;
- individual assignment giving money;
- class is over instantly giving more creative tasks;
- family relations are fine to teach to express one's thoughts in full;
- begin with existing knowledge it is necessary to teach to deliver to others.

Of course, it is not an easy task to develop a task that activates students, keeps their attention, and has a creative character. The successful formation of independent thinking in elementary school students takes place only on the basis of taking into account the main features of their creativity by the teacher. To do this, it is necessary to solve the main tasks that allow the development of creative thinking of students. In addition, this work is a collective work of the organizers of primary education, analysis of theoretical sources dedicated to the organization of independent learning activities of students at the first stage of education in the future, as well as general secondary education. the study of the work experience of the institutions allows to clarify the following pedagogical conditions for organizing the creative activity of elementary school students: developing the program "I learn independent thinking" for the development of independent (creative) cognitive activity of students of junior school age and puts the issues of implementation in the primary school educational process on the agenda. Young people with developed creative thinking, independent thinking, confidence in their own knowledge, personal opinion, steadfastness in their beliefs show their incomparable help in further development of our society and successful implementation of democratic reforms.

In conclusion, from the first stages of school education, it is one of the important tasks of today to educate intellectual young people who are ready to think in a new way and to perceive correctly different relationships, situations and situations.

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